

EXPLORING THE KEY DRIVERS OF TOURISTS' REVISIT INTENTIONS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

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Abstract: Increasing visitors' intention to return to a tourist destination is one of the key factors in maintaining the competitiveness of a tourist destination. However, identifying the key determinants that influence return visit intentions remains a challenge in the tourism literature. This study aims to uncover the key factors that influence visitors' intention to return, through a systematic literature review. This study utilized the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) method, where relevant scientific articles published in the last five years (2020-2024) were identified and screened from leading databases namely Scopus, Web of Science, Crossref, and Google Scholar by Elsevier, Sage, Taylor & Francis, MDPI, & Emerald to ensure broad and in-depth coverage. A total of 65 articles that met the inclusion criteria were further analyzed. To enrich the analysis, bibliometric techniques with VOSviewer software were used to map the relationships between the identified factors, providing visual insights into research trends and dominant topic clusters. The results show that travel experience, traveler loyalty, destination image, visitor satisfaction, service quality, and perceived value are the main determinants that contribute significantly to revisiting intentions. This study also identified a gap in the literature regarding the impact of digital technology and sustainability on revisiting intentions, opening up opportunities for further research. The findings are expected to contribute to the development of tourism theory as well as provide practical guidance for stakeholders in designing effective strategies to improve visitor retention.

Keywords: Revisit Intention, Travelers, Tourism, Systematic Literature Review, PRISMA, VOS viewer.

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Introduction

In recent decades, the tourism industry has become one of the most dynamic and rapidly growing sectors of the global economy. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), in 2019, the number of international tourists reached 1.5 billion, an increase of 4% compared to the previous year. This trend shows the importance of tourism as a major contributor to economic growth in many countries, including developing countries that rely heavily on income from the tourism sector (Rasool et al., 2021). However, the COVID-19 pandemic that hit the world in 2020 had a significant impact on this industry, emphasizing the need for effective strategies to maintain and increase the number of tourist visits in the future. In the highly competitive tourism industry, understanding the factors that influence visitors' intention to return to a destination is a crucial aspect in designing effective marketing and tourism product development strategies (Mihai et al., 2023; Abbasi et al., 2021).

Revisiting intentions not only reflect visitor satisfaction but also have direct implications for loyalty and long-term revenue of tourist destinations (Viet et al., 2020; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2021).

One of the key strategies in restoring and sustaining the tourism sector is to understand the factors that encourage tourists to return to a destination (Pessoa et al., 2022; González-Rodríguez et al., 2023; Vu et al., 2022; Bayih & Singh, 2020; Chiawo et al., 2023). Return visit intentions are an important indicator of the long-term sustainability of tourist destinations, in addition to reflecting tourists' satisfaction with their experiences (Torres-Moraga et al., 2024; Thipsingh et al., 2022). In this context, an in-depth understanding of the key drivers of return visit intentions is crucial, especially for developing effective and sustainable marketing strategies. While many studies have explored various aspects of the travel experience, there is still uncertainty regarding the specific determinants that influence visitors' decision to return. Some studies emphasize the importance of customer satisfaction, while others highlight service quality or overall experience.

However, there is little consensus regarding the most influential factors and how they interact with each other. In addition, the development of digital technologies and the increasingly important trend of sustainability in the tourism industry have not been fully explored in the context of tourists' return visit intentions.

To address this gap, this study aims to uncover the key drivers that influence travelers' revisit intentions through a systematic literature review. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) method is used to ensure that the review is conducted in a systematic and transparent manner, by identifying relevant articles from reputable databases and applying strict selection criteria (Moher et al., 2010). In addition, bibliometric analysis using VOSviewer will be conducted to visualize the relationship between the various determinants identified (Martins et al., 2022). This research is expected to provide valuable insights for academics, practitioners, and policy makers in formulating effective strategies to increase visitor satisfaction and loyalty, as well as maximizing the long-term potential of tourist destinations.

Methods

This study used a systematic literature review approach following the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) protocol which can be seen in Figure 1 to ensure a transparent and structured review process. The PRISMA procedure includes several steps: 1) Identification: Relevant articles are identified from reputable scientific databases. Databases used in this study include Scopus, Web of Science, Crossref, and Google Scholar by Elsevier, Sage, Taylor & Francis,

MDPI, & Emerald to ensure breadth and depth of coverage, 2) Screening: Articles found through the initial search were screened based on relevance to the topic and research methodology. The screening process was done by examining abstracts and keywords to ensure conformity with the research criteria, 3) Eligibility: Articles that passed the initial screening were further examined to evaluate their methodological feasibility and quality. Eligibility criteria included clear methodology, relevance to visitors' revisiting intentions, and significant theoretical or practical contributions, 4) Inclusion: Articles that met all eligibility criteria were included in the final analysis. The inclusion process is followed by data extraction for further analysis.

In this study, to ensure that the literature reviewed covered the most relevant and up-to-date perspectives and methods, three major databases, namely Scopus, Web of Science, Crossref, and Google Scholar, were used. The search was conducted using the keywords “tourist revisit intentions”, “determinants of revisit”, “tourism loyalty”, and “visitor repeat behavior”. The search was limited to articles published within the last 5 years (2020-2024). This limitation was imposed to ensure that the literature review included recent research that is still relevant to current trends and dynamics in tourism. The focus on English-language articles ensures that the results of this review can be accessed and used by the global scientific community. In addition, only articles relevant to the topic of visitor revisit intentions were included, ensuring that the review remains focused and provides deep insights into the key determinants in this context.

Figure 1. PRISMA SLR Logic Flow Diagram (2020-2024)

Source: Adapted from Haddaway et al (2020)

In the literature screening process for this systematic review, the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) approach was used to ensure transparency and rigor in the selection of relevant studies. The process involved several stages illustrated in the PRISMA flow chart, starting from the identification of literature sources to the final inclusion of relevant studies. The initial stage began with a literature search through four major databases, namely Scopus, Web of Science, Crossref and Google Scholar. This search identified 200 relevant articles, based on predefined keywords, such as “tourist revisit intentions,” “determinants of revisit,” “tourism loyalty,” and “visitor repeat behavior.” These keywords focus on visitors' revisit intentions and the factors that influence this decision. After the identification stage, all articles found through the database search were included in the initial list for further evaluation. At this stage, a total of 200 articles were evaluated based on title and abstract to assess their relevance to the research topic. Predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria were used in this screening. The inclusion criteria used included: 1) Articles that address factors that influence visitors' return visit intentions to tourist destinations, 2) Articles that use clear and justifiable methodologies, including empirical studies, comprehensive literature reviews, or meta-analyses, 3) Articles published between 2020 and 2024, 4) Articles published in English, 5) Articles that are directly related to visitor revisit intentions and make a significant contribution to the understanding of the topic. In contrast, exclusion criteria included articles that were irrelevant to the topic, did not meet methodological standards, or that were published in non-peer-reviewed journals (Figure 1).

The next stage was a further screening of 200 articles based on abstracts and full text. Articles that were irrelevant, duplicative, or that did not meet the inclusion criteria were removed from the list. This screening process is important to ensure that only truly relevant and high-quality articles will be analyzed further. After screening, a total of 135 articles were eliminated because they did not fit the research criteria, such as irrelevant topics, unmet methodological standards, or publication in non-peer-reviewed journals. Ultimately, 65 articles that met the inclusion criteria were selected for further analysis. This systematic review focused on the final set of 65 articles identified from Scopus, Web of Science, Crossref, and Google Scholar databases, within the publication time range of 2020 to 2024, with predefined keywords, accessed on August 23, 2024. As a basis for the bibliometric analysis to be conducted, the database was compiled using Microsoft Excel, where information related to indicators such as year of publication, journal, number of publications by country, journal impact factor, and country ranking based on Scimago were entered for further analysis.

Results

From the bibliometric analysis conducted based on the number of publications per year from 2020 to 2024, there is significant variation in the distribution of publications over the period. Figure 2 illustrates the percentage of annual publications as follows.

Figure 2. Number of Publications per Year (2020-2024)

Source: Data Processing Results (2024)

In 2020, publications in this area accounted for 15% of the total research identified, while in 2021 there was a slight increase to 18%. This trend continued in 2022 with the percentage of publications reaching 17%. However, a significant spike was seen in 2023, where related publications peaked at 31% of the total research, signaling a large increase in academic interest in this topic. This may be related to the recovery of the global tourism sector post-COVID-19 pandemic, where strategies to increase visitor loyalty are particularly relevant. By 2024, the number of publications decreases slightly to 18%, although this data may still be evolving. Overall, this distribution reflects how the dynamics of research in the topic of traveler revisiting intentions are evolving, with a notable increase in 2023 signaling a productive period in scientific publications in this area.

The number of publications per journal from 2020 to 2024 shows that research related to tourists' revisiting intentions is spread across various journals, with some journals showing more significant contributions. Of the 26 journals identified in table 1, the Journal of Destination Marketing & Management ranked the highest with a total of 7 publications, confirming its role as one of the key platforms in this research. Furthermore, Heliyon contributed 4 publications, while Cogent Business & Management and Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights had 3 publications each. Several other journals, including Cogent Social Sciences, International Journal of Tourism Cities, Journal of Tourism Futures, and Sage Open, contributed 2 publications each. The remaining publications are spread across other journals with only 1 publication each. This distribution shows that while there are a few journals that take center stage in tourist return intentions research, many other journals also contribute to spreading knowledge in this area.

Table 1. Number of Publications per Journal (2020-2024)

Journal	Number of Publications per Journal
Administrative Sciences	1
Annals of Tourism Research Empirical Insights	1
Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research	1
Cities	1
Cogent Business & Management	3

Cogent Social Sciences	2
Economies	1
European Research on Management and Business Economics	1
Foods	1
Future Business Journal	1
Heliyon	4
International Journal of Geoheritage and Parks	1
International Journal of Hospitality Management	1
International Journal of Tourism Cities	2
Journal of Destination Marketing & Management	7
Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research	1
Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights	3
Journal of Innovation & Knowledge	1
Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism	1
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research	1
Journal of Tourism Futures	2
Journal of Travel Research	1
Journal of Vacation Marketing	1
KnE Social Sciences	1
Land	1
Sage Open	2
Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC	2
Sustainability (Switzerland)	14
Tourism Management	2
Tourism Management Perspectives	3
Tourism Review	1

Source: Data Processing Results (2024)

Figure 3 provides an overview of the geographical origin of research related to tourist return visit intentions. From the data illustrated, most of the research originated from China, with a total of 15 publications, indicating a dominant contribution in this field. Multinational research, involving several countries in their studies, accounted for 10 publications, signaling an international collaborative approach in this research. Indonesia followed with 9 publications, indicating significant research interest and activity in the region. Vietnam also contributed with 8 publications. In addition, a number of other studies were scattered with the number of publications varying from 1 to 2 per country. This distribution reflects a high concentration of research in a few key countries as well as a broader international contribution to the study of traveler return visit intentions.

Figure 3. Number of Publications by Country

Source: Data Processing Results (2024)

Table 2 presents data related to journal and country rankings according to Scimago Journal and Country Rank (SJR), best quartile, and H index by publication.

Table 2. Journal Impact Factor and Scimago Country Rank

Journal	SJR 2023	Best Quartile	H Index
Administrative Sciences	0.63	Q2	35
Annals of Tourism Research Empirical Insights	1.06	Q1	13
Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research	1.05	Q1	62
Cities	1.73	Q1	127
Cogent Business & Management	0.57	Q2	44
Cogent Social Sciences	0.38	Q2	27
Economies	0.5	Q2	34
European Research on Management and Business Economics	1.42	Q1	36
Foods	0.87	Q1	97
Future Business Journal	x	x	x
Heliyon	0.62	Q1	88
International Journal of Geoheritage and Parks	0.66	Q1	19
International Journal of Hospitality Management	2.92	Q1	169
International Journal of Tourism Cities	0.77	Q1	29
Journal of Destination Marketing & Management	2.45	Q1	75
Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research	1.33	Q1	88
Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights	0.97	Q1	23
Journal of Innovation & Knowledge	3.37	Q1	54
Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism	0.85	Q2	40

Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research	0.89	Q1	47
Journal of Tourism Futures	1.15	Q1	33
Journal of Travel Research	3.41	Q1	172
Journal of Vacation Marketing	1.32	Q1	78
KnE Social Sciences	x	x	x
Land	x	x	x
Sage Open	0.51	Q1	60
Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC	0.91	Q2	30
Sustainability (Switzerland)	0.67	Q1	169
Tourism Management	3.35	Q1	255
Tourism Management Perspectives	1.97	Q1	82
Tourism Review	1.76	Q1	58

Source: Data Processing Results (2024)

Among the listed journals, *Tourism Management* stands out with the highest ranking, recording an SJR of 3.35 and being in quartile 1 (Q1), with an impressive H index of 255. This indicates that *Tourism Management* is one of the leading journals in tourism

with significant impact and visibility. In addition, of the total contributions, 23 were published in journals in quartile 1 (Q1), indicating a high prevalence of quality research in this category. A total of 6 contributions were published in quartile 2 (Q2), while 3 contributions had no data available regarding their quartile. These data provide insights into the quality and impact of journals publishing research related to traveler return visit intentions, as well as the distribution of research contributions within the various journal quartiles.

Figure 4 displays a network visualization for keywords frequently used in research on tourist return visits. From this bibliometric analysis, it can be seen that these keywords form two main clusters, each represented by a different color. The first cluster, shown in red, consists of keywords such as customer satisfaction, eco-friendly hotels, perceived quality, perceived value, and revisit intention. The keywords in this cluster indicate a focus on customer satisfaction, perceived quality, perceived value, and intention to return to an eco-friendly hotel. Meanwhile, the second cluster consists of keywords such as destination image, loyalty, rural tourism, satisfaction, and tourist satisfaction. This cluster centers on destination image, tourist loyalty, rural tourism, and tourist satisfaction. These two clusters, although different in their specific focus, are interrelated in the context of research on tourist revisit intentions, suggesting that various factors such as experience, satisfaction, destination image, and loyalty play an important role in encouraging tourists to return to a destination.

Figure 4. Bibliographic Keyword Network

This bibliometric study was conducted to investigate and identify indicators related to tourist return visits. Using the scientific software VOSviewer, this study aims to identify the main keywords that frequently appear in studies focusing on factors affecting tourist return visits. In Figure 5, the results of the analysis conducted using VOSviewer show that keywords provided by the authors and appearing more than ten times in the database were registered in the analysis. This analysis resulted in two clusters, with a total of 20 items, 184 links, and a total link strength of 1236.

Figure 5. Network Visualization for All Keywords by Title and Abstract

VOSviewer provides a visualization called the overlay visualization, which can be seen in Figure 6. This visualization clarifies the network of keywords that appear in each scientific article, allowing us to understand the topics being researched by researchers as well as identify potential future research trends. In this visualization, we can observe that the keyword “revisit intention” appears frequently and is related to other keywords such as tourist satisfaction, perception, hotel, revisit, intention, tourist, value, impact, behavioral intention, relationship, satisfaction, effect, destination image, behavior, destination, visitor, tourism, and factor. These terms refer to key concepts often associated with research on tourist revisits, indicating a significant research focus on tourist satisfaction, destination image, and visitor behavior.

Figure 6. Overlay Visualization for Keyword “Revisit Intention”

Discussion

In the following sections, insights have been gathered from the literature included in this review and set the analysis around three dimensions of revisit intentions: 1) traveler experience and traveler loyalty, 2) destination image and traveler satisfaction, 3) tourism and hospitality.

1. Traveler Experience and Traveler Loyalty

A positive experience, reflected in visitor satisfaction and loyalty, is often the main driver that makes visitors choose to return to the same destination (Carvache-Franco., 2022). In addition, the determinants and effects of such experiences are also in focus in the reviewed literature. The overall travel experience was also found to be a key determinant affecting revisiting intentions. For example, research by (Stylidis, 2022; Karim et al., 2024) suggests that the quality of the tourist experience, including interactions with locals, services received, and accessibility of facilities, plays an important role in determining whether visitors will return to a particular destination. Traveler loyalty is a recurring theme in the literature, with various studies showing that loyalty serves as a key predictor of repeat visit intentions. Studies (Cong, 2021; Omo-Obas & Anning-Dorson., 2023) state that loyalty is built through consistent positive experiences and strong relationships between visitors and destinations, which in turn encourage visitors to return. This loyalty is also reinforced by factors such as satisfactory service and the presence of unique attractions in the destination (Hung et al., 2021).

The study by (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2022) shows that positive tourism experiences have a direct influence on visitor satisfaction and their intention to return. Experiences involving cultural interaction, natural beauty, and adequate service often contribute to high satisfaction, which significantly increases the intention to revisit the tourist destination. Research by (Afshardoost & Eshaghi, 2020) examined the relationship between destination image, tourism experience, and visitor loyalty. They found that a strong destination image, combined with a satisfying tourism experience, creates greater loyalty among visitors, which leads to the intention to make a repeat visit. This loyalty is not only driven by destination quality, but also by how visitors process their experiences (Zulvianti et al., 2023).

According to research by (Baghirov et al., 2023; Mehra, 2023), deep emotional experiences and active involvement of visitors in tourism activities have a major effect on intention to return. This study shows that the higher the level of visitor involvement in activities organized by the destination, the more likely they are to return. This involvement can be in the form of participation in local activities, interaction with the local community, or unique experiences that cannot be found elsewhere. Research by (Manyangara et al., 2023) highlights the importance of service experience and the quality of interactions with destination staff in shaping repeat visit intentions. They found that friendly, professional and responsive service creates a more satisfying experience for visitors, which in turn increases their desire to return. The study also noted that perceptions of service quality are often influenced by initial expectations and direct interactions during the visit.

According to (Peng et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2020) in their research identified that tourist experiences that are unique and different from other destinations can be a strong driver of repeat visit intentions. They noted that visitors who feel they have experienced something extraordinary or exclusive in a destination are likely to develop an emotional attachment to the place, which influences their decision to return in the future. Studies by (Bai & Chang, 2023; Joo et al., 2021) found that social interactions with fellow visitors, as well as with local residents, enrich the tourist experience and increase the likelihood of visitors to return. Positive interactions, both through shared activities and through communication with locals, create deeper memories and strengthen the intention to repeat the visit.

Recent research by (Kusumastuti et al., 2024) shows that tourist destinations that offer sustainable experiences, such as good environmental management and support for local communities, can increase visitors' intention to return. Tourism experiences that support sustainability not only provide moral satisfaction to visitors, but also strengthen the emotional connection with the destination. These studies consistently show that a positive tourism experience, encompassing various aspects such as service, social interaction, destination image and sustainability, strongly influences visitors' intention to return. Destination managers can use these findings to design effective strategies to increase visitor loyalty and ensure higher repeat visits.

2. Destination Image and Visitor Satisfaction

The reviewed research often associates a positive image of the destination with high levels of satisfaction, which in turn increases visitors' intention to repeat visits. Destination image is identified as an important factor influencing visitors' intention to return. In a study conducted by (Abbasi et al., 2021), a positive destination image was found to have a strong correlation with repeat visit intentions, especially among visitors who had a previous positive experience. This research also shows that marketing efforts that focus on improving destination image can increase visitor loyalty and increase the chances of repeat visits.

Destination image is often considered a key factor in attracting and retaining tourists. Several studies have shown that a positive destination image significantly influences visitors' intention to return to the destination. According to (Scofield et al., 2020) in his research shows that a strong and positive destination image not only attracts new tourists but also influences the decision of previous visitors to make a repeat visit. This research emphasizes that the visual and symbolic elements of destination image play an important role in building tourist perceptions (Adamus-Matuszyńska et al., 2021; de Castro Mendes & Jose Cavenaghi, 2020). A positive destination image can create a favorable perception of the quality of the experience to be received, which ultimately drives return intentions (Gorji et al., 2023). They also found that effective image management can strengthen traveler loyalty and increase repeat visits.

Visitor satisfaction has been widely recognized as an important predictor in determining repeat visit intentions. Travelers who are satisfied with their experience are more likely to return to the same destination in the future. Studies by (Nazir et al., 2021; Milan Čulić et al., 2021; Tang et al., 2022) in their research found that tourist satisfaction plays a mediating role between destination image and intention to return. This study suggests that satisfaction

is a direct result of positive perceptions of the destination, which then drives the desire to repeat the visit. Research by (Al-Msallam, 2020; Cheng et al., 2022) also confirmed that tourist satisfaction directly affects intention to return. They found that satisfied travelers tend to have a stronger emotional connection with the destination and are more likely to recommend it to others, as well as return to visit it.

Integration of destination image and satisfaction in predicting return intentions. Several studies have attempted to integrate these two concepts to better understand how destination image and satisfaction together influence return visit intentions. The study by (Apriani et al., 2023) in their study concluded that destination image and tourist satisfaction have a synergistic effect on intention to return. They showed that a good destination image can increase visitor satisfaction, which then significantly increases the likelihood of repeat visits. Trang et al. (2023) investigated the role of destination image and satisfaction in influencing traveler loyalty and intention to return. The study found that destination image influences traveler satisfaction, and this satisfaction then becomes a key determinant of loyalty and revisit intentions. Previous studies have shown that destination image and visitor satisfaction are two key factors that are interrelated in influencing visitors' intention to return. A positive destination image not only attracts new travelers but also strengthens repeat visit intentions through increased satisfaction. Thus, a deeper understanding of how these two factors interact can provide valuable insights for destination managers in improving visitor loyalty and encouraging repeat visits.

3. Tourism and Hospitality

High-quality hospitality services and unique tourism attractions play a central role in influencing visitors' decision to return to the destination (Ramadhani et al., 2024; Nguyen, 2021). Several studies by (Huu et al., 2024; Lim et al., 2024; Chang & Lin, 2022) examined the relationship between traveler satisfaction at hotels and intention to return. These studies found that factors such as room quality, staff friendliness, and added value provided by the hotel have a great influence on customer satisfaction, which in turn increases loyalty and intention to return. Travelers who are satisfied with their stay at the hotel are more likely to choose to return to the same destination. A study by (Nieves-Pavón et al., 2024; Salah et al., 2023) showed that traditional Word of Mouth (WOM) as well as Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM) play an important role in influencing travelers' intention to return. Positive reviews from other travelers, either in person or through online platforms, can encourage travelers' intention to revisit a particular destination or hotel (Su et al., 2022; Fazal-e-Hasan et al., 2024; Zou & Yu, 2022; Zheng et al., 2023).

According to research by (Yang et al., 2024; Acampora et al., 2022; Sánchez-Franco & Aramendia-Muneta, 2023), hospitality service quality, including aspects such as cleanliness, staff friendliness, and accommodation comfort, strongly influences travelers' intention to return. This research emphasizes that improving service quality in the hospitality sector can contribute significantly to increasing customer loyalty and intention to revisit. Research by (Deb et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2024) found that the commitment of destinations and hospitality facilities to sustainable practices can increase tourists' intention to return. Travelers who care about the environment are more likely to return to destinations

that show real efforts in environmental preservation and sustainable resource management (Fauzi et al., 2024; Kokkhangplu et al., 2023; Macdonald et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2023). Service quality perceived by travelers, especially in the hospitality sector, is a strong predictor of repeat visit intentions (Chi et al., 2020). Travelers who perceive that the service they receive matches or exceeds their expectations tend to have a higher intention to return.

Studies by (Xu et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2023) show that the first impression formed by travelers during their first visit, be it at the hotel or at the destination in general, strongly influences their intention to return. A positive first impression, which includes a warm welcome and service efficiency, can encourage travelers to plan a repeat visit. Research by (Zhu et al., 2024; Solakis et al., 2022) shows that the perceived price and value received by travelers from a destination or hospitality service also play an important role in their intention to return. Travelers who feel that they are getting good value for their money are more likely to return to the same destination.

Conclusion & Recommendation

Traveler satisfaction is shown to be the most significant determinant factor in influencing return visit intentions. High satisfaction related to service quality, travel experience, and perceived value by tourists consistently drives the desire to return. Destination image plays an important role in strengthening revisit intentions. A positive image, which includes perceptions of safety, beauty, and facilities, is able to build tourists' loyalty to a destination. The emotional attachment formed between tourists and the destination was also found to be an important factor. Travelers who have a strong emotional attachment to a destination are more likely to revisit in the future. ease of access and infrastructure are also key factors that cannot be ignored. Destinations with good accessibility and supportive infrastructure are more likely to attract repeat visits from tourists.

However, the study also revealed some gaps in the literature that need further investigation. For example, the role of digital technology in shaping revisit intentions and the interaction between local cultural factors and tourist behavior remain under-researched. As a recommendation, future research should expand the focus on less explored factors, including the impact of technological innovation and cultural dynamics on revisit intentions. In addition, empirical studies that test integrative models of the various factors identified are also urgently needed to provide a more holistic understanding. Thus, this review not only enriches the theoretical understanding of return visit intention, but also provides practical insights for destination managers in designing more effective and sustainable marketing strategies.

Continued Research

Tourists' intention to visit again is formed because of tourists' positive experiences when visiting tourist destinations, this is supported by local wisdom and community culture as well as the role of digitalization in promoting tourist destinations. Further research can focus on the role of digitalization and local community wisdom in increasing tourist return visits.

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References

1. Abbasi, G.A., Kumaravelu, J., Goh, Y.-N. & Dara Singh, K.S. (2021), "Understanding the intention to revisit a destination by expanding the theory of planned behaviour (TPB)", *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, Vol. 25 No. 2, pp. 282-311. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SJME-12-2019-0109>
2. Acampora, A., Preziosi, M., Lucchetti, M.C., & Merli, R. (2022). The Role of Hotel Environmental Communication and Guests' Environmental Concern in Determining Guests' Behavioral Intentions. *Sustainability*, 14(18), 11638. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141811638>
3. Adamus-Matuszyńska, A., Dzik, P., Michnik, J., & Polok, G. (2021). Visual Component of Destination Brands as a Tool for Communicating Sustainable Tourism Offers. *Sustainability*, 13(2):731. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020731>
4. Afshardoost, M., & Eshaghi, M.S. (2020). Destination image and tourist behavioural intentions: A meta-analysis, *Tourism Management*, 81, 104154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2020.104154>.
5. Al- Msallam, S. (2020). The impact of tourists' emotions on satisfaction and destination loyalty – an integrative moderated mediation model: tourists' experience in Switzerland. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 3(5), 509-528. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-11-2019-0126>
6. Apriani, A., Meliantari, D., Febrian, W.D., Herawati, Y., Windayanti, (2023). Determinants of E-WOM and Intention to Revisit Beach in Yogyakarta Indonesia Post-pandemic Through Visitor Satisfaction. *Transdisciplinary Symposium on Business, Economics, and Communication, KnE Social Sciences*, 803–816. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v8i12.13726>
7. Baghirov, F., Bozbay, Z. & Zhang, Y. (2023). Individual factors impacting tourist satisfaction and revisit intention in slow tourism cities: an extended model. *International Journal of Tourism Cities*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJTC-05-2023-0094>
8. Bai, S., & Chang, H.-H. (2023). Effect of Tourist-To-Tourist Encounters: Increased Conflict or Reduced Social Distance? *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 47(1), 207-234. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10963480211014938>
9. Bayih, B.E., & Singh, A. Modeling domestic tourism: motivations, satisfaction and tourist behavioral intentions. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e04839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04839>.
10. Carvache-Franco, M., Carvache-Franco, W., Pérez-Orozco, A., Viquez-Paniagua, A.G., & Carvache-Franco, O. (2022). Satisfaction Factors That Predict Loyalty in Ecotourism: A Study of Foreign Tourism in Costa Rica. *Land*, 11(1):125. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11010125>
11. Chang, T-Y., & Lin, Y-C. (2022). The Effects of Atmosphere on Perceived Values and Customer Satisfaction toward the Theme Hotel: The Moderating Role of Green Practice Perception. *Sustainability*, 14(15), 9153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14159153>
12. Chen, X., Cheng, Z-f., Kim, G-B. (2020). Make It Memorable: Tourism Experience, Fun, Recommendation and Revisit Intentions of Chinese Outbound Tourists. *Sustainability*, 12(5):1904. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12051904>
13. Cheng, Y., Hu, F., Wang, J., Wang, G., Innes, J.L., Xie, Y., Wang, G. (2022). Visitor satisfaction and behavioral intentions in nature-based tourism during the COVID-19 pandemic: A case study from Zhangjiajie National Forest Park, China. *International Journal of Geoheritage and Parks*, 10(1), 143-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgeop.2022.03.001>.
14. Chi, X., Lee, S.K., Ahn, Y-j., & Kiatkawsin, K. (2020). Tourist-Perceived Quality and Loyalty Intentions towards Rural Tourism in China. *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3614. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093614>
15. Chiawo, D., Haggai, C., Muniu, V., Njuguna, R., & Ngila, P. (2023). Tourism Recovery and Sustainability Post Pandemic: An Integrated Approach for Kenya's Tourism Hotspots. *Sustainability*, 15(9):7291. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097291>
16. Cong, L.C. (2021). Perceived risk and destination knowledge in the satisfaction-loyalty intention relationship: An empirical study of european tourists in vietnam. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 33, 100343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jort.2020.100343>.
17. Čulić, M., Vujičić, M.D., Kalinić, Č., Dunjić, M., Stankov, U., Kovačić, S., Vasiljević, Đ.A., & Anđelković, Ž. (2021). Rookie Tourism Destinations—The Effects of Attractiveness Factors on Destination Image and Revisit Intention with the Satisfaction Mediation Effect. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 5780. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13115780>
18. de Castro Mendes, B., & Jose Cavenaghi, A. (2020). Building a destination image: images of exclusiveness and refuge, *International Journal of Tourism Cities*, 6(4), 673-690. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJTC-09-2019-0150>
19. Deb, M., Sharma, V.K., & Panchapakesan, P. (2023). Sustainable practices, mindfulness, tranquility, and well-being: A mixed-method approach. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 30, 100816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2023.100816>
20. Fauzi, M.A., Hanafiah, M.H. & Kunjuraman, V. (2024). Tourists' intention to visit green hotels: building on the theory of planned behaviour and the value-belief-norm theory, *Journal of Tourism Futures*, 10(2), 255-276. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JTF-01-2022-0008>
21. Fazal-e-Hasan, S. M., Mortimer, G., Ahmadi, H., Adil, M., & Sadiq, M. (2024). Examining the impact of tourists' hope, knowledge and perceived value on online hotel booking intentions. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 29(6), 719–735. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10941665.2024.2343058>
22. González-Rodríguez, M.R., Díaz-Fernández, M.C., & Pulido-Pavón, N. (2023). Tourist destination competitiveness: An international approach through the travel and tourism competitiveness index. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 47, 101127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2023.101127>.

23. Gorji, A.S., Garcia, F.A., & Mercadé-Melé, P. (2023). Tourists' perceived destination image and behavioral intentions towards a sanctioned destination: Comparing visitors and non-visitors. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 45, 101062. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2022.101062>.
24. Haddaway, NR, Page, MJ, Pritchard, CC, & McGuinness, LA (2022). PRISMA2020: Paket R dan aplikasi Shiny untuk menghasilkan diagram alir yang sesuai dengan PRISMA 2020, dengan interaktivitas untuk transparansi digital yang dioptimalkan dan Open Synthesis Campbell Systematic Reviews, 18, e1230. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cl2.1230>
25. Hung, V.V., Dey, S.K., Vaculcikova, Z., & Anh, L.T.H. (2021). The Influence of Tourists' Experience on Destination Loyalty: A Case Study of Hue City, Vietnam. *Sustainability*, 13(16):8889. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13168889>
26. Joo, D., Xu, W., Lee, J., Lee, C-Kwoosnam, K.M. (2021). Residents' perceived risk, emotional solidarity, and support for tourism amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 19, 100553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2021.100553>.
27. Karim, R.A., Rabiul, M.K., & Arfat, S.M. (2024), Factors influencing tourists' behavioural intentions towards beach destinations: the mediating roles of destination experience and destination satisfaction, *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 7(4), 2033-2054. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-04-2023-0276>
28. Kokkhangplu, A., Onlamai, W., Chokpreedapanich, T., & Phikul, K. (2023). What Predicts Behavioral Intention in Eco-Friendly Hotels? The Roles of Tourist's Perceived Value and Satisfaction: A Case Study of Thailand. *Sustainability*, 15(4), 3219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15043219>
29. Kusumastuti, H., Pranita, D., Viendyasari, M., Rasul, M.S., & Sarjana, S. (2024). Leveraging Local Value in a Post-Smart Tourism Village to Encourage Sustainable Tourism. *Sustainability*, 16(2):873. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16020873>
30. Lim, W.M., Jasim, K.M., & Das, M. (2024). Augmented and virtual reality in hotels: Impact on tourist satisfaction and intention to stay and return. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 116, 103631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2023.103631>.
31. Liu, L. W., Wang, C. C., Pahrudin, P., Royanow, A. F., Lu, C., & Rahadi, I. (2023). Does virtual tourism influence tourist visit intention on actual attraction? A study from tourist behavior in Indonesia. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2240052>
32. Macdonald, C., Turffs, D., McEntee, K., Elliot, J., & Wester, J. (2023). The relationship between tourism and the environment in Florida, USA: A media content analysis. *Annals of Tourism Research Empirical Insights*, 4(1), 100092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annale.2023.100092>.
33. Manyangara, M. E., Makanyeza, C., & Muranda, Z. (2023). The effect of service quality on revisit intention: The mediating role of destination image. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.22502nguy64>
34. Martins, J., Gonçalves, R. & Branco, F. A bibliometric analysis and visualization of e-learning adoption using VOSviewer. *Univ Access Inf Soc* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-022-00953-0>
35. Mehra, P. (2023). Unexpected surprise: Emotion analysis and aspect based sentiment analysis (ABSA) of user generated comments to study behavioral intentions of tourists. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 45, 101063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2022.101063>.
36. Mihai, V.C., Dumitras, D.E., Oroian, C., Chiciudean, G.O., Arion, F.H., & Mureşan, I.C. 2023. Exploring the Factors Involved in Tourists' Decision-Making and Determinants of Length of Stay. *Administrative Sciences*, 13(10):215. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci13100215>
37. Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D.G. (2010). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *International Journal of Surgery*, 8(5), 336-341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsu.2010.02.007>.
38. Nazir, M.U., Yasin, I., & Tat, H.H. (2021). Destination image's mediating role between perceived risks, perceived constraints, and behavioral intention. *Heliyon*, 7(7), e07613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07613>.
39. Nguyen Huu, T., Nguyen Ngoc, H., Nguyen Dai, L., Nguyen Thi Thu, D., Truc, L. N., & Nguyen Trong, L. (2024). Effect of tourist satisfaction on revisit intention in Can Tho City, Vietnam. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2322779>
40. Nguyen Viet, B., Dang, H. P., Nguyen, H. H., & Foroudi, P. (2020). Revisit intention and satisfaction: The role of destination image, perceived risk, and cultural contact. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1796249>
41. Nguyen, Q.H. (2021). Impact of Investment in Tourism Infrastructure Development on Attracting International Visitors: A Nonlinear Panel ARDL Approach Using Vietnam's Data. *Economies*, 9(3), 131. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies9030131>
42. Nguyen, T. D., Nguyen, N. T., & Thanh, N. N. (2024). Factors Affecting Sustainable Tourism Development: Evidence from the Central Highlands of Vietnam. *Sage Open*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241240816>
43. Nieves-Pavón, S., López-Mosquera, N., & Jiménez-Naranjo, H. The role emotions play in loyalty and WOM intention in a Smart Tourism Destination Management. *Cities*, 145, 104681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2023.104681>.
44. Omo-Obas, P., & Anning-Dorson, T. (2023). Cognitive-affective-motivation factors influencing international visitors' destination satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 6(5), 2222-2240. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-05-2022-0178>
45. Peng, J., Yang, X., Fu, S., & Huan, T-C. (2023). Exploring the influence of tourists' happiness on revisit intention in the context of Traditional Chinese Medicine cultural tourism. *Tourism Management*, 94, 104647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2022.104647>.
46. Pessoa, R.A., Oliveira, O., & Souza, L.L.F. (2022), "Factors that make a destination fascinating and motivate (re)visit", *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, 26(2), 210-230. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SJME-12-2021-0231>

47. Ramadhani, D.P., Alamsyah, A., Febrianta, M.Y., & Damayanti, L.Z.A. (2024). Exploring Tourists' Behavioral Patterns in Bali's Top-Rated Destinations: Perception and Mobility. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 19(2):743-773. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer19020040>
48. Rasool, H., Maqbool, S. & Tarique, M. (2021). The relationship between tourism and economic growth among BRICS countries: a panel cointegration analysis. *Futur Bus J*, 7, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-020-00048-3>
49. Rasoolimanesh, S.M., Seyfi, S., Hall, C.M., Hatamifar, P. (2021). Understanding memorable tourism experiences and behavioural intentions of heritage tourists. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*. 21, 100621. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2021.100621>.
50. Rasoolimanesh, S.M., Seyfi, S., Rather, R.A. & Hall, C.M. (2022), Investigating the mediating role of visitor satisfaction in the relationship between memorable tourism experiences and behavioral intentions in heritage tourism context, *Tourism Review*, 77(2), 687-709. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-02-2021-0086>
51. Salah, M.H.A., Abdou, A.H., Hassan, T.H., El-Amin, M.A-MM., Kegour, A.B.A., Alboray, H.M.M., Mohamed, A.S.D., Ali, H.S.A.M., & Mohammed, E.F.A. (2023). Power of eWOM and Its Antecedents in Driving Customers' Intention to Revisit: An Empirical Investigation on Five-Star Eco-Friendly Hotels in Saudi Arabia. *Sustainability*, 15(12), 9270. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15129270>
52. Sánchez-Franco, M.J., & Aramendia-Muneta, M.E. (2023). Why do guests stay at Airbnb versus hotels? An empirical analysis of necessary and sufficient conditions. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2023.100380>
53. Schofield, P., Coromina, L., Camprubi, R., & Kim, S. (2020). An analysis of first-time and repeat-visitor destination images through the prism of the three-factor theory of consumer satisfaction. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 17, 100463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2020.100463>.
54. Solakis, K., Peña-Vinces, J., & Lopez-Bonilla, J.M. (2022). Value co-creation and perceived value: A customer perspective in the hospitality context. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28(1), 100175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2021.100175>.
55. Styliadis, D. (2022). Exploring Resident–Tourist Interaction and its Impact on Tourists' Destination Image. *Journal of Travel Research*, 61(1), 186-201. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287520969861>
56. Su, L., Yang, Q., Swanson, S. R., & Chen, N. C. (2022). The impact of online reviews on destination trust and travel intention: The moderating role of online review trustworthiness. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 28(4), 406-423. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13567667211063207>
57. Tang, H., Wang, R., Jin, X., & Zhang, Z. (2022). The Effects of Motivation, Destination Image and Satisfaction on Rural Tourism Tourists' Willingness to Revisit. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 11938. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141911938>
58. Thipsingh, S., Srisathan, W. A., Wongsachia, S., Ketkaew, C., Naruetharadhol, P., Hengboriboon, L., & Wong, J. (2022). Social and sustainable determinants of the tourist satisfaction and temporal revisit intention: A case of Yogyakarta, Indonesia. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2022.2068269>
59. Torres-Moraga, E., Rodriguez-Sanchez, C., Alonso-Dos-Santos, M., & Vidal, A. (2024). Tourscape role in tourist destination sustainability: A path towards revisit, *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 31, 100863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2024.100863>.
60. Trang, N.T., Yoo, J.J-E., Joo, D., Lee, G. (2023). Incorporating senses into destination image. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 27, 100760. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2022.100760>.
61. UNWTO. (20 Januari 2020). International tourism growth continues to outpace the global economy, URL <https://www.unwto.org/international-tourism-growth-continues-to-outpace-the-economy>
62. Vu, H.D., Nguyen, A.T.N., Nguyen, N.T.P. & Tran, D.B. (2022). Impacts and restoration strategy of the tourism industry post-COVID-19 pandemic: evidence from Vietnam, *Journal of Tourism Futures*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JTF-09-2021-0218>
63. Xu, F., Niu, W., Li, S., & Bai, Y. (2020). The Mechanism of Word-of-Mouth for Tourist Destinations in Crisis. *Sage Open*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020919491>
64. Yang, L., Hu, X., Lee, H.M., & Zhang, Y. (2023). The Impacts of Ecotourists' Perceived Authenticity and Perceived Values on Their Behaviors: Evidence from Huangshan World Natural and Cultural Heritage Site. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1551. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021551>
65. Yang, S., Liu, Y., & Xu, L. (2024). The effect of food tourism experiences on tourists' subjective well-being. *Heliyon*, 10(3), e25482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e25482>
66. Zheng, Y-H., Xu, T., Shi, G., & Jiang, L. (2023). I want to go there too! Tourism destination envy in social media marketing. *Heliyon*, 9(12), e22889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e22889>.
67. Zhu, Y., Zhu, L., & Weng, L. (2024). How Do Tourists' Value Perceptions of Food Experiences Influence Their Perceived Destination Image and Revisit Intention? A Moderated Mediation Model. *Foods*, 13(3):412. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13030412>
68. Zou, Y., & Yu, Q. Sense of safety toward tourism destinations: A social constructivist perspective. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 24, 100708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2022.100708>.
69. Zulvianti, N., Aimon, H., & Abror, A. (2023). Perceived Environmental Value, Destination Image, and Tourist Loyalty: The Role of Tourist Satisfaction and Religiosity. *Sustainability*, 15(10):8038. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15108038>